

Guidelines and Recommendations

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Recommendations for the study of monoclonal gammopathies in the clinical laboratory. A consensus of the Spanish Society of Laboratory Medicine and the Spanish Society of Hematology and Hemotherapy. Part III: Clinical and analytical recommendations for the study of monoclonal gammopathies by MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry

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Abstract: Monoclonal gammopathies (MGs) represent a diverse group of plasma cell disorders that range from asymptomatic premalignant conditions to aggressive malignancies such as multiple myeloma (MM). Mass

spectrometry (MS) based serum analysis offers a non-invasive, highly sensitive alternative to conventional techniques for identifying and quantifying M-proteins. It enables more precise assessment of treatment response and residual disease, particularly in patients with suspected complete response (CR), those not eligible for bone marrow procedures, or those treated with monoclonal antibodies that may interfere with standard assays. This guideline document,

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endorsed by the Spanish Society of Laboratory Medicine (SEMEDLAB) and the Spanish Society of Hematology (SEHH), provides comprehensive recommendations for the clinical and analytical application of MS in the detection and monitoring of M-proteins in patients with MGs. The document outlines optimal use of MS at diagnosis, during follow-up, and in reporting practices, with a focus on standardized implementation, interpretative criteria, and clinical decision-making support.

Keywords: monoclonal; gammopathies; mass spectrometry; myeloma; recommendations; MRD

Introduction

Monoclonal gammopathies (MGs) constitute a heterogeneous spectrum of disorders characterized by the clonal proliferation of plasma cells (PCs), generally within the bone marrow (BM). This clonal expansion typically results in the overproduction and secretion of a monoclonal immunoglobulin (Ig) or protein (M-protein) into the bloodstream and/or urine. The concentration of this M-protein serves as a surrogate marker for tumor burden, thereby providing a quantitative measure proportional to the disease burden. The clinical manifestations of MG can range from an indolent, asymptomatic premalignant state named monoclonal gammopathy of uncertain significance (or MGUS) to the highly aggressive malignancy known as multiple myeloma (MM) [1–3].

Over the past two decades, significant advances have been made in the treatment of MM. The incorporation of novel therapeutic agents into standard treatment regimens has markedly improved patient outcomes, resulting in higher response rates and progressively longer median

survival times. Currently, it is commonplace for most MM patients, particularly those receiving first-line treatment, to achieve complete response (CR). The International Myeloma Working Group (IMWG) defines CR as the complete disappearance of the M-protein as detected by conventional diagnostic techniques, specifically serum protein electrophoresis (SPE) and immunofixation electrophoresis (IFE) in both serum and urine, along with a bone marrow plasma cell percentage of less than 5% and disappearance of any soft tissue plasmacytomas [4].

Nevertheless, despite the high rates of CR, these patients often experience relapse, highlighting the persistence of the disease, also known as measurable residual disease (MRD). This persistent disease, which drives disease progression in patients who achieve CR, remains undetectable by conventional methods due to their limited sensitivity. Numerous studies have demonstrated that achieving MRD negativity has a significant prognostic value, being associated with longer progression-free survival (PFS) and overall survival (OS) in all patients with MM. Given this clinical significance, MRD must be evaluated using more sensitive methods to assess disease response. In this context, MRD can be determined in BM samples through techniques that evaluate the presence of residual tumor cells using high-sensitivity flow cytometry (Next Generation Flow; NGF) or next-generation sequencing (NGS) techniques. If MRD is negative in the bone marrow, it is essential to assess for the presence of extramedullary disease using imaging techniques such as PET-CT [5]. However, despite their high sensitivity, all these techniques have several limitations and drawbacks: they are invasive and therefore painful, require specialized personnel, and since the extraction is from a single sample, it may not be representative of the cellularity in the BM due to the patchy infiltration typical of MM or the possibility that

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Table 1: Comparison between the main strategies for identifying M-proteins by mass spectrometry. Table adapted from Guan et al. [8].

	Intact immunoglobulin methods			Clonotypic methods
	QIP-MS (EXENT system)	MASS-FIX	miRAMM	M-Insight/Easy M
Sample type	Serum	Serum Urine	Serum	Serum Urine
Sample volume	Serum: 100 µL	Serum: 20 µL Urine: 1 mL	Serum: 50 µL Urine: 25 µL	Serum: 2 µL
Detection target	Intact M-protein	Intact M-protein	Intact M-protein	Specific peptides
Baseline sample	Required	Required	Required	Required
Quantification	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Analytical sensitivity (LOQ)	15 mg/L ^a	100 mg/L	50 mg/L (LC) 250 mg/L (HC)	0.2 mg/L
Time to result	Hours	2–5 days	Not found	3–5 days
Emergent M-proteins	Yes	Yes	Yes	No (only tracks M-protein at diagnosis)
For clinical lab	Yes	No: service	Not found	No: service
IMWG endorsed	Yes: in lieu of IFE	Yes: in lieu of IFE	No	No
IVDR certified	Yes	No	No	No

M-protein, monoclonal protein; LOQ, limit of quantification; IMWG, International Myeloma Working Group; IFE, immunofixation; IVDR, *in vitro* diagnostics regulation; HC, heavy chains; LC, light chains. ^aLOQ was established under conditions that replicate immunoparesis.

the sample is hemodiluted by the aspirate, increasing the likelihood of a false-negative result [6]. Additionally, imaging techniques also face significant limitations in assessing MRD as the potential for excessive radiation exposure to the patient, which raises safety concerns, and the complexity involved in accurately interpreting the results, which can be challenging and subjective. All of these factors constrain the frequency with which invasive and imaging techniques can be employed in clinical practice, thereby limiting their utility in the regular monitoring and assessment of MRD [7]. Therefore, methods based on the identification and quantification of M-protein in serum by mass spectrometry (MS) are currently being developed to achieve a sensitivity and specificity that provides better prognostic information compared to standard methods.

MS measures the mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) of M-proteins, specific of each patient and tumor clone, based on their unique amino acid sequences, generated through the processes of recombination and somatic hypermutation within the complementarity-determining regions (CDRs). Briefly, the sample is ionized, and ions are separated by m/z , generating spectra that are interpreted by software to indicate the presence and intensity of specific M-proteins. The main strategies for identifying M-proteins by MS are summarized in Table 1. They include clonotypic methods that involve trypsin digestion of Igs to identify patient-specific target peptides. This approach requires sequencing the V(D)J gene rearrangement of Igs at diagnosis. Subsequent serum samples undergo digestion and analysis using LC-MS/MS (LC: liquid chromatography) for detection and quantitative

monitoring. Although theoretically more sensitive, these methods are complex and time-consuming, and no robust clinical data are available yet. The Intact Ig Methods detect and quantify the molecular mass of intact heavy and/or light chains by techniques like miRAMM, using ESI-Q-TOF (Electrospray Ionization Quadrupole Time-of-Flight), and MALDI-TOF-based methods (MASS-SCREEN, MASS-FIX, QIP-MS) [9]. MASS-SCREEN and MASS-FIX were developed by the Mayo Clinic and QIP-MS (quantitative immunoprecipitation-mass spectrometry) was developed by The Binding Site part of ThermoFisher Scientific. QIP-MS is currently commercialized and available on the market featuring automated sample preparation and user-friendly software, enabling standardized application. Moreover, this technology has received IVDR approval, allowing its use in Europe [10]. These MALDI-TOF methods are faster and more cost-effective, making them the most suitable option for routine use.

Objective and scope of application

The purpose of Part III of this document is to provide recommendations for using Mass Spectrometry (MS) when an M-protein is already detected with an alternative method or there is strong clinical suspicion of a MG of clinical significance. It outlines the laboratory results report model and the recommended frequency for monitoring. Additionally, it highlights the clinical benefits of MS over conventional methods in monitoring patients with Multiple Myeloma (MM), noting that MS offers higher sensitivity and

specificity as compared with standard techniques, enabling more accurate detection and quantification of M-proteins.

Methods

The guidelines presented in this document are based on the currently available scientific evidence and the insights of experts in MGs from both the clinical laboratory and hematology disciplines. These recommendations have been endorsed by the Spanish Society of Laboratory Medicine (SEMEDLAB) and the Spanish Society of Hematology (SEHH). The scientific evidence supporting these guidelines is referenced throughout the document, while recommendations not directly supported by published data are based on the consensus of the expert panel involved in their development. No studies involving human participants or animals were conducted for the development of these guidelines. Therefore, ethical approval was not required.

Brief description of the intact Ig MALDI-TOF method

The analysis of serum samples using it involves three main steps: sample preparation, analysis of the samples in the MALDI-TOF mass spectrometer, and the identification and quantification of monoclonal Igs using a specialized software. Each step will be detailed below.

Sample preparation

In general, the sample preparation process includes:

- **Immunoenrichment of Igs:** The serum sample is diluted and divided into five aliquots in a dilution plate. Each aliquot receives paramagnetic beads coated with a specific antibody (IgG, IgA, IgM, total kappa, and total

lambda; no IgD and IgE beads are yet available). After an incubation period, the Igs in the sample bind to the specific antibody on the beads.

- **Washing:** The aliquot plates are placed on a magnetic base that attracts and holds the paramagnetic beads, allowing a series of washes to isolate the Igs bound to the beads during incubation.
- **Elution:** After washing, the selected Igs are incubated with acetic acid to dissociate them from the paramagnetic beads.
- **Separation of heavy and light chains:** During the same incubation, a reducing agent is added to break the disulfide bonds connecting the Ig chains, thereby separating them into their respective heavy and light chains.
- **Application on MALDI plate:** The beads are again attracted by the magnetic plate, allowing the suspended sample to be collected and automatically pipetted onto a metal plate for the MALDI-TOF analyzer using the matrix-sample-matrix application method.
- **Drying:** Once the sample is applied, it is left to dry for 10 min to co-crystallize with the matrix.

MALDI-TOF analysis

This step includes two sub-steps:

- **Ionization (MALDI):** The solidified sample within the matrix receives a laser pulse in high vacuum, which excites the matrix and transfers energy in the form of protons (H^+) to the sample, thereby positively charging and ionizing it. The irradiated area heats up and ejects the ions into the gas phase.
- **Time-of-flight analyzer (TOF):** A high-power electric field accelerates the generated ions, which then travel to a detector at different speeds according to their m/z ratio. The lower the m/z ratio of the ions, the faster they reach the detector. The detector records the different m/z signals received, as well as the intensity of the number of ions with the same m/z that arrive simultaneously.

Figure 1: Comparison of polyclonal and monoclonal light chain profiles by mass spectrometry. (A) Mass distribution of light chains in the serum of a healthy control: the lambda light chains appear first due to their lower m/z ratio compared to the kappa light chains. (B) Identification of a peak with a specific m/z ratio above the polyclonal background in a serum sample with an M-protein.

Data analysis and interpretation of spectra

The detected signal is transformed using the software into five spectra, one for each immunoprecipitation done in the first step (IgG, IgA, IgM, total kappa, and total lambda), within a range of 10,900 to 13,600 Da. Each spectrum shows the mass distribution of the light chains, with two protonation charges (+2H). Each class of Ig forms two types of distributions based on the light chains. The λ chain distribution presents a normal distribution, while the κ chain consists of two normal distributions: the kappa chain and the heavy kappa chain, a kappa chain variant with higher molecular mass generated by the rearrangement of the IGKV2 and IGKV49 germline genes. On the x-axis, the m/z ratio directly represents the molecular mass of the protein, and on the y-axis, the intensity of the peaks represents the abundance of the proteins (Figure 1). In a healthy control (Figure 1A), the mass spectrum will show a polyclonal distribution of light chains due to the polyclonal production of Igs. However, when a peak with a specific m/z and higher intensity above this polyclonal background is detected, it is identified as a possible M-protein (Figure 1B).

The spectral peaks of the Ig light chain are automatically identified and matched between the spectra of the IgG, IgA, and IgM and the total light chains (kappa and lambda), thus identifying the isotype of the M-protein. Quantification is performed indirectly through an algorithm that combines the detected peak area for each Ig with the concentration of total IgG, IgA, and IgM.

Once all possible spectral peaks are identified in the clinical and temporal context of the patient (diagnosis or follow-up), the results to assess the presence or absence of the M-protein should be reviewed and validated:

- At diagnosis: All detected monoclonal peaks will be identified and quantified, with their isotype and m/z ratio, as a possible M-protein (Figure 2A).
- At follow-up: The detected monoclonal peaks will allow the identification of the patient's M-protein based on the isotype and m/z of the M-protein identified at diagnosis. Other detected monoclonal peaks could correspond to oligoclonal proteins, interferences or less likely potentially new B-cell/PC clones. For patient follow-up, the EXENT platform defines the same M-protein as one observed within $\pm 4 m/z$ of the diagnostic clone. This threshold is supported by the instrument's dual calibration strategy, which applies both external (per plate) and internal (per spot) calibrations to ensure high mass accuracy. According to manufacturer data, this longitudinal mass accuracy of $\pm 4 m/z$ has been validated following CLSI guidelines. While variability beyond this

threshold could theoretically still represent the same monoclonal protein, applying a $\pm 4 m/z$ window provides a robust and standardized criterion for clinical reporting and minimizes the risk of misclassification. (Figure 2B).

Therefore, it is important that results are always evaluated in the context of the patient clinical history. If the analyzed sample is a follow-up sample, the m/z ratio of the baseline M-protein needs to be known to avoid confusion with any other oligoclonal Igs, as treatment will decrease the concentration of M-protein and increase the probability of the presence of these proteins due to cellular reactivity.

Analytical challenges to detect, identify and quantify M-proteins by MALDI-TOF MS

The results will be automatically interpreted by the specific software; however, there are minimum requirements that must be considered to ensure a quality result [11]:

M-protein detection

- For each light chain MS spectrum, the kappa and/or lambda distribution should be considered as a control to ensure that the polyclonal kappa and lambda chains from each isotype are detected.
- A peak should only be considered monoclonal if it is detected above the polyclonal background.
- In the MALDI-TOF workflow, matrix adduct peaks are automatically recognized and paired with the primary monoclonal peak (typically at +75 Da). While they are excluded from being reported as independent peaks, they are incorporated into the monoclonal peak model used for quantification. Thus, the peak area measurement reflects the combined contribution of the primary and adduct peaks, and this integrated value is propagated through to the reported concentration.
- It should be noted when reporting the results that the clinical significance of a monoclonal protein detected in serum at a concentration below 0.2 g/L remains unknown [12].
- Known interferences may appear within the same light chains distribution, such as the +2 charge states C1q, or therapeutic monoclonal antibodies (mAb) (Table 2) [13].

M-protein identification

The monoclonal peak from an intact Ig should be detected and matched between the light chain spectra (G, A, or M) and the total lambda or kappa spectra. If the monoclonal protein is identified in a known patient and appears only in the G, A, or M light chain spectra, it is recommended to report the presence of an intact M-protein, only when the M-protein isotype in the

(A)

(B)

Figure 2: Results from the mass spectrometry analysis (QIP-MS) of a serum sample from a patient with newly diagnosed IgG kappa MM. (A) The 5 spectra showing the distribution of the light chains corresponding to each specific antibody are shown, with the monoclonal spectral peak identified and automatically quantified based on the total Ig concentration values. In this case, an IgG kappa M-protein has been identified in a serum sample from a newly diagnosed patient. A matrix adduct can frequently be observed as a second small peak at +75 Da from the MP. (B) Mass spectrometry analysis of a serum sample from the same patient shown in Figure 2A, analyzed during treatment monitoring, where the IgG kappa has been identified with the same m/z as at diagnosis. Moreover, the presence of an IgA lambda oligoclonal peak, a small peak above the polyclonal background with different m/z ratios than the M-protein, is observed, along with a peak with the same m/z ratio identified as the therapeutic monoclonal antibody isatuximab (11,745.1 m/z), marked with the “Q” indicator, coded as “Isat”.

Table 2: List of the most common interferents observed by MS.

Type of interferent	Interferent	Measured <i>m/z</i> (± 2 charge)
Endogenous interferents	C1q – A-chain	13,789
	C1q – B-chain	12,809
	C1q – C-chain	12,020
Pharmacological interferents	Daratumumab	11,693
	Elotuzumab	11,714
	Isatuximab	11,746
	Elranatamab	12,049 and 11,810
	Talquetamab	11,820 and 11,303
	Teclistamab	11,317 and 11,302
	Linvoseltamab	11,709

patient is already known. This is because the polyclonal background is generally lower in these spectra compared to the total light chain spectra, which can interfere with detection, and the light chains associated with the heavy chains are still being identified.

Furthermore, if the detected monoclonal peak is identified only in the total kappa or lambda spectra, but absent in the IgG, IgA, or IgM light chain spectra, the possibility of an IgD or IgE M-protein should be considered together with a light chain MM.

M-protein quantification

The M-protein concentration is automatically calculated by the software (Figure 3).

Recommendations for when to request MS determination

At diagnosis

Ideally, mass spectrometry analysis of serum samples should be performed in all patients with malignant MGs

Figure 3: Equation to quantify M-protein peaks detected by the MS, relating the modeled light chain peak area to total immunoglobulin concentration. In cases where the EXENT system technology is used, total Ig must be measured using optilite analyzer, as indicated in the technical data sheet.

when a new M-protein is detected in serum and/or urine using conventional methods (SPE, IFE) and free light chains quantification (FLC), which are particularly indicated in light chain MM and patients with AL amyloidosis. Besides, in cases where results from these standard techniques are negative, but there remains a high clinical suspicion of MG, analysis by MS may also be considered.

Performing this analysis at the time of screening or/and diagnosis is essential for quantifying and identifying the isotype and *m/z* of the patients MP, enabling its identification in future analyses with the highest sensitivity and specificity. This helps avoid confusion with other oligoclonal proteins (that may appear in response to treatment, inflammatory processes, etc.) as well as for detecting, identifying, and quantifying other low-concentration M-proteins that are not detected by conventional methods due to the increased sensitivity of the technique since the patient could progress with one of them [14].

If no diagnostic serum sample is available to determine the M-protein *m/z*, any sample where the M-protein is still visible in SPE can be used as a reference for MS characterization and follow-up. If no such reference exists, MS can still identify an M-protein when a peak exceeds the LOQ, rises above the polyclonal background, and matches the known diagnostic isotype. If multiple peaks of the same isotype are present at baseline, the peak with highest concentration should be considered the M-protein [15]. In all cases, the suspected M-protein should be confirmed by monitoring its evolution in subsequent samples. In addition, it is important to detect the presence of post-translational modifications (PTM) in the identified M-protein, which are characterized by a broad *m/z* distribution composed of multiple peaks, giving it a “crown-like” appearance (Figure 4). This can affect various Ig biological processes, such as stability, half-life, binding capacity, interaction with other proteins, and even their degradation or secretion. Therefore, the identification of this PTM, at screening/diagnosis, could have a significant clinical value. Most notably, it is considered a risk factor for progression in patients with MG, and is associated with a higher risk of developing AL amyloidosis (AL) or cold agglutinin disease [15–18].

Patients' follow up

The recommendations for using MS to monitor patients undergoing treatment once their M-protein has been identified will be divided into two groups: clinical and analytical recommendations.

Figure 4: Serum sample analyzed by mass spectrometry showing a glycosylated IgA-lambda molecular mass, identified as 'mass shift light chain' (MSL) or light chain peak(s) with detected mass shift.

Clinical recommendations

These recommendations apply only to the monitoring of patient response after treatment and cannot currently be used for clinical decision-making. Nevertheless, due to the objective data provided by M-protein measurements and the superior sensitivity of MS over conventional methods, its use could be considered in the following situations. The clinical recommendations are summarized in Figure 5.

Following the recommendations of the International Myeloma Working Group (IMWG), when a patient is suspected of having achieved a CR due to a negative serum IFE, a BM aspirate should be performed to confirm the CR and, most importantly, to assess the presence of MRD. At the same time, since the MP is no longer detectable in serum by conventional methods, monitoring can continue using MS, monthly if the patient is receiving active treatment, or every 2–3 months if the patient is not on therapy.

Based on the combined results of MRD in bone marrow and MS in serum, four scenarios may arise:

- (1) **MRD+ & MS+:** In a patient who is MRD+ and MS+, monitoring could be performed using MS. Once MS becomes negative, a repeat BM aspirate should be considered. When MS results become negative, it is also highly likely that the patient is MRD-negative in the BM, given the high negative predictive value (NPV) of this technique, especially in later stages of treatment [20, 21].
- (2) **MRD+ & MS-:** If MS remains negative, a repeat BM aspirate is recommended at 6 months to assess for MRD status. Conversely, if MS becomes positive during follow-up, close monitoring should be ensured since there is a high likelihood of disease progression in a short period of time (<1 year) [20].
- (3) **MRD- & MS+:** This discordance may reflect delayed clearance of the MP, particularly in IgG MM, or may result from a false-negative MRD result (such as in cases

Figure 5: Proposed algorithm for the management of residual disease: M-protein by MS assessment in serum samples and MRD assessment in bone marrow samples in MM patients with suspected complete or stringent complete response. Suspected CR stands for conventional methods being negative or not evaluable (such as in the case of free light chains). MRD assessment should be done following IMWG guidelines [19].

with patchy or extramedullary disease not captured in the BM sample). If MS remains persistently positive during follow-up or especially if the amount of the MP increases, a new BM aspirate for MRD as well as PET/CT imaging should be performed.

- (4) **MRD– & MS–:** Double negative patients should be closely monitored with MS since, as stated before, if MS becomes positive during follow-up, close monitoring should be ensured since there is a high likelihood of disease progression in a short period of time (<1 year). [20]. If MS remains negative during the monthly or every 2–3 months follow-up, MRD in BM should be performed yearly.

Finally, from a clinical perspective, it is important to consider the benefit of monitoring patients who, for any reason, do not undergo BM aspiration/biopsy (i.e., elderly or frail patients). In this context, the availability of a minimally invasive technology with sensitivity levels close to those of MRD presents a significant advantage. Thus, MS should be considered once these patients achieve suspected CR, as it allows for more accurate monitoring compared to conventional methods, which fail to adequately reflect the depth of responses achieved by today's highly effective treatments.

Analytical recommendations

The following analytical recommendations are summarized in Figure 6.

- In patients whose M-protein can no longer be quantified by SPE (an M-protein level below the SPE detection limit of 1 g/L should not be reported [1]), MS provides a more sensitive and objective quantitative assessment of the treatment response compared to IFE [22]. Indeed, following the IMWG Mass Spectrometry Committee recommendations, we endorse the detection of M-proteins by MS as an alternative to IFE for clinical practice and clinical trials [8]. In this regard, the Spanish Myeloma Group has confirmed the superior sensitivity of MS compared to conventional methods in the context of the GEM2012/GEM2014MAIN clinical trials. The findings from this trials demonstrated that MS was able to discriminate between two groups with statistically significant PFS among patients who, according to the International Myeloma Working Group (IMWG) criteria, were in suspected complete response (CR) [20].
- When the patient's treatment includes a monoclonal antibody that may interfere with the identification and quantification of the M-protein by both SPE and IFE, MS

Figure 6: Proposed algorithm for M-protein assessment in serum samples at diagnosis and during response evaluation in multiple myeloma patients. The dotted arrow indicates the protocol to follow when replacing IFE with MS. The green and red arrows indicate to follow-up by the technique indicated. IT: immunotyping.

can specifically discriminate the M-protein, ensuring accurate monitoring [21, 23, 24].

- For M-protein of the IgM isotype, due to the high probability of polymerization, SPE may yield inadequate quantification, and by IFE some bands may be observed that act as interferences due to interactions with other serum Igs; in contrast, in our experience and due to the Ig purification during the pre-analytical process, MS could provide more precise measurements [25, 26]. However, since immunoturbidimetry is used to calculate M-protein concentration by MS it could be expected an overestimation when compared to SPE due to the systematic differences previously described [27].
- M-proteins that migrate into a region of the SPE other than the gamma region may coexist with other serum

proteins, making their quantification potentially overestimated or difficult to achieve; MS can overcome these challenges by providing more accurate results because the rest of the serum proteins are eliminated during the pre-analytical process [28].

Recommendations for reporting the results

The report of the M-protein (MP) study by MS should include (Figure 7):

- In accordance with the requirements of ISO 15189:2022 for clinical laboratories, the report must include

MALDI-TOF Mass spectrometry:

Methodology:	Quantitative Immunoprecipitation MALDI-TOF (QIP-MS) – EXENT® Analyzer
Monoclonal protein:	Positive
Isotype:	IgG kappa
Mass to charge (m/z):	11697,1
Concentration:	3.47 g/L
Interpretation:	Monoclonal protein IgG kappa previously identified during the follow-up. <i>Presence of oligoclonal peaks, possibly reactive due to immunological response, transplantation or drugs. It will be monitored in subsequent serum samples.</i>

Figure 7: Example fragment from a global laboratory report (protein results section) of MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry (QIP-MS) results of a known patient with IgG kappa MM, where the patient’s M-protein was identified at its known m/z (11,697.1) with a concentration of 3.47 g/L, along with the presence of oligoclonal peaks.

essential information such as clear patient and sample identification, demographic details, relevant clinical information if provided, date of the study, the center performing the test, as well as the names or identifiers of the requesting physician and the person responsible for validation or reporting.

- Methodology and equipment used.
- Detection of one or more M-protein/s.
 - The presence of the M-proteins detected should be reported as a positive/negative result. If one or more peaks are detected for the first time in a diagnosis serum sample, the result should be reported as positive; in a follow-up sample, only the M-protein(s) identified at diagnosis should be reported as a positive result.
 - If the detected M-protein shares the same m/z as any mAb, the potential administration of the mAb should be investigated with the patient’s therapeutic history or in consultation with the hematologist. If confirmed, it should be taken into account for accurate M-protein monitoring by MS.
 - Any new potential M-proteins detected during follow-up should be reported with the isotype and concentration information as a commentary in the interpretative comments section (Table 3) and monitored throughout the treatment to determine whether they represent or not transient proteins or a new peak.
- Identification of one or more M-protein.
 - The isotype of the identified M-protein/s should be reported and indicated as “not previously identified” if the sample is from baseline, or as “previously identified” if the M-protein has been detected before, in the interpretative comments.
 - The m/z of the identified M-proteins should be reported. The m/z corresponds to the molecular mass of the M-protein, which should always be the same value ± 4 m/z difference, as indicated in the technical data sheet. If the M-protein is identified as with PTMs, the m/z should be reported as the range

Table 3: List of the most common interpretative commentaries.

M-protein identification	M-protein (isotype, e.g. IgG kappa) not previously identified, or M-protein (isotype, e.g. IgG kappa) previously identified during the follow-up.
New M-protein detected	An M-protein (isotype) not previously identified (xx, xxx.x m/z , e.g., 11,678.3 m/z) (x.x g/L, e.g., 3.2 g/L). Its presence and concentration will be monitored in subsequent serum samples.
Oligoclonal peaks	Presence of oligoclonal peaks, possibly reactive due to immunological response, transplantation or drugs. It will be monitored in subsequent serum samples.
Post-translational modifications	M-protein with light chains post-translational modifications. It may indicate higher risk of MG progression, AL amyloidosis, or cold agglutinin disease.

covered by the cluster of peaks detected, rather than as a single isolated peak.

- The concentration of the each M-protein/s identified.
 - Should be included and expressed in g/L.
 - Currently, the method is only available for quantifying MPs that have an intact total Ig IgG, IgA, or IgM, but not for free light chains MP. In these cases, for now, the result can only be reported qualitatively as “present”. When the concentration of the M-protein is below the limit of quantification (LOQ), it should only be reported qualitatively as “present”.
- An interpretative comments section where the following statements should be included (Table 3):
 - New M-protein detected: if a new M-protein not previously identified has been detected in the patient’s follow-up, its isotype, m/z and concentration should be reported. The presence of oligoclonal peaks should be reported as “Presence of oligoclonal peaks, possibly reactive due to immunological response, transplantation or drugs”. If the m/z of any of the oligoclonal peaks remains along the treatment, we recommend to

report it along with their concentration to characterize their evolution and if they become a potential new or additional M-protein. Although this occurrence is rare, there are reports that document such conversions [22].

- The presence of light chains PTM of the M-protein: If the M-protein is identified with MPT, this should be identified as “M-protein with light chains post-translational modifications” and it should be accompanied with an interpretative comment that describe the possible clinical implications: “The presence of this modifications could be considered as risk factor for progression in patients with MG or as a higher risk of developing AL amyloidosis (AL) or cold agglutinin disease”.
- Any interpretative comment about the analyzed sample that is considered appropriate to add.

Limitations and future perspectives

Given that MS is a relatively novel technique for the detection and quantification of M-proteins, it inherently presents certain limitations and areas ripe for further development. One limitation arises from the extremely low prevalence of IgD or IgE isotype MM. Due to this rarity, the development of immunoprecipitation beads tailored specifically for these Igs has not been a primary focus. Consequently, patients with IgE or IgD isotype MM must continue to be monitored using conventional methodologies, such as SPE and/or sIFE. These traditional techniques remain indispensable and are the currently recommended methods for accurately assessing the progression and therapeutic response in these patients. In addition, the comparatively higher cost of MS relative to these techniques currently limits its routine application for the analysis of serum samples in the hospital setting.

Moreover, it should be noted that in the intact immunoglobulin MALDI-TOF approach as implemented in QIP-MS, the analysis is restricted to the 10,900–13,600 m/z window, which corresponds to the +2 charge state of immunoglobulin light chains. This provides an optimal balance of signal intensity and spectral resolution. However, this capture window does not interrogate potential abnormalities occurring at alternative charge states (+1, +3) or outside of this range, and thus does not allow direct assessment of heavy chain diseases. Furthermore, recently reported light chain fragments [29] may manifest outside this analytical window. Although their clinical significance remains uncertain, manufacturer data indicate that such cases have consistently

resulted in the detection of one or more abnormal peaks. These considerations highlight that the reported capture window is specific to the QIP-MS (EXENT) platform and is not necessarily generalizable to other intact immunoglobulin methods, such as MASS-FIX or miRAMM. Furthermore, a critical factor to have in mind is the need for a baseline diagnostic sample to accurately assess patient responses and identify relapses. Without this initial reference, interpreting follow-up measurements becomes more challenging. Nevertheless, this issue can be mitigated by tracking consecutive samples for a stable and consistent m/z peak that persists over time, provided that the isotype also matches the one identified at diagnosis, thereby distinguishing it from transient oligoclonal peaks and enabling reliable disease monitoring. Additionally, a baseline sample could also be considered as that obtained when a patient meets the criteria for progression established by conventional methods [30].

Another current limitation of this technology is the lack of commercial availability of beads for immunoprecipitating FLCs. This limitation is particularly significant for the diagnosis and monitoring of patients with light chain myeloma (LCMM), also known as Bence Jones myeloma, as well as for patients with primary amyloidosis. The absence of these specialized beads hampers the effective application of MS in these cases, as FLCs play a crucial role in the pathology and progression of these conditions. Nonetheless, these beads are currently under development and are expected to be commercially available in the near future. Moreover, it is worth noting that these beads have also been shown to increase the sensitivity of QIP-MS in patients with intact Ig multiple myeloma [22].

Conclusions

Mass spectrometry is a highly valuable tool for monitoring patients with MGs, conditions characterized by the presence of an abnormal Ig (M-protein) produced by a plasma cell clone. The identification and quantification of M-protein are crucial for diagnosis, prognosis, and evaluating treatment response. MS offers a non-invasive method, with high sensitivity and specificity, allowing for the assessment of treatment effectiveness, offering a gateway for MRD detection and enabling relapse prediction. In this document, we propose a guide for integrating MS into daily clinical practice.

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Use of Large Language Models, AI and Machine Learning

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